

Remarkable photo-induced anticancer activity of vitamin-B6 Schiff base copper(II) complexes of pyridyl bases[†]

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Abstract : Vitamin-B6 (VB6) Schiff base (H₂L) copper(II) complexes of pyridyl bases, viz. [Cu(bpy)(L)] (1), [Cu(phen)(L)] (2) and [Cu(dppz)(L)] (3), where bpy is 2,2'-bipyridine, phen is 1,10-phenanthroline and dppz is dipyrido[3,2-*a*:2',3'-*c*]phenazine are synthesized, characterized and their photo-induced anticancer activity studied. The non-electrolytic one-electron paramagnetic complexes exhibit a d-d band near 700 nm in DMF. The dppz complex intercalatively binds to calf-thymus DNA with binding constant (K_b) values of $\sim 10^6$ M⁻¹. This complex exhibits low chemical nuclease activity but excellent DNA photocleavage activity when irradiated with red light of 705 nm forming [•]OH radical. It displays remarkable photocytotoxicity in human cervical cancer cells (HeLa) giving IC₅₀ value of 0.9 μ M in visible light (400–700 nm) while being less toxic in darkness (IC₅₀ : 23 μ M). The cellular uptake of the complexes seems to be via VB6 transporting membrane carrier mediated diffusion pathway. Photo-induced cell death follows apoptotic pathway involving photo-generated intracellular reactive oxygen species.

Keywords : Medicinal chemistry, copper, dipyridophenazine, vitamin B6 Schiff base, photocytotoxicity, cellular apoptosis.

Introduction

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is a novel method to treat cancer where the photoactive drug is selectively activated by visible or near-IR light to kill the cancer cells, leaving the unexposed healthy cells unaffected¹⁻³. PDT has the potential to overcome the side effects and drug resistance of currently used chemotherapeutic drugs⁴. Photofrin[®], an oligomeric mixture of haematoporphyrin derivative (HpD), is the FDA approved PDT drug⁴. This drug suffers from side effects like hepatotoxicity due to oxidative conversion to bilirubin causing jaundice and skin sensitivity causing unwanted rashes^{4,5}. To counter these side effects associated with the macrocyclic organic dyes, the chemistry of metal-based PDT agents is developed in recent times⁶⁻¹⁰. The coordination complexes having bio-essential constituents are shown to be non-toxic in the dark but become potentially cytotoxic on photo-activation in visible light. The metal complexes with their varied coordination chemistry and photophysical properties could be potential al-

ternatives to the FDA approved PDT drug Photofrin^{®6-10}. Metal complexes in general show photo-induced cytotoxicity via generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS)¹⁰. We have earlier reported copper(II) complexes of phenanthroline bases showing visible light-induced photocytotoxicity but with lower PDT effect due to significant dark toxicity arising from the generation of hydroxyl radicals in reducing cellular thiols¹¹⁻¹³. Reduction of copper(II) to copper(I) by glutathione (GSH) is facile forming radicals that damage the cells leading to dark toxicity. This being a major predicament for cellular applications of copper(II) complexes in PDT, designing suitable copper(II) complexes having redox stability is of importance. Tuning the redox potential of the metal center can be achieved with proper choice of the coordinating ligands. To reduce the dark toxicity and to enhance the PDT effect we have designed and synthesized new ternary copper(II) complexes, viz. {B-(Cu^{II})-L} in which the bio-essential metal ion is chosen as copper(II) for its low-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

energy d-d band and for its bio-essentiality, Schiff base ligand H_2L in dianionic form with a vitamin-B6 moiety to enhance the cellular uptake of the complex in the cancer cells, and planar DNA intercalative pyridyl bases (B), viz. 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and photo-active dipyrido[3,2-*a*:2',3'-*c*]phenazine (dppz)^{14,15}. Vitamin-B₆ (VB6) is a versatile co-factor required for many biochemical processes^{16,17}. The cellular uptake of VB6 involves its diffusion through the transporting membrane carrier (VTC)¹⁸. The rapidly dividing cancer cells have a high requirement for VB6 for their growth. Metal complexes having this moiety could achieve VTC mediated preferential uptake into the cancer cells over the normal cells¹⁹.

Herein, we report the synthesis, characterization, DNA binding and visible light-induced photocytotoxicity of the copper(II) complexes of VB6 Schiff base (H_2L) and pyridyl ligands, viz. [Cu(bpy)(L)] (1), [Cu(phen)(L)] (2) and [Cu(dppz)(L)] (3) (Fig. 1). Complex 1 having 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy) was used as a control to study the photocytotoxic potential of phen and dppz complexes in a ternary structure. Significant results of this work include : (i) remarkable photocytotoxicity in visible light of the dppz

Fig. 1. Complexes 1-3 and the ligands used.

complex 3 in HeLa cells while being less-toxic in the dark, (ii) the dppz complex inducing apoptotic cell death by generation of intracellular ROS only upon light irradiation, (iii) complex 3 showing low chemical nuclease activity but excellent DNA photo-cleavage activity in near-IR light of 705 nm forming $\cdot OH$ radical and (iv) displaying excellent binding affinity to ct-DNA with its extended aromatic phenazine moiety. The photocytotoxic potential of complex 3 compares well to that of Photofrin[®].

Experimental

Materials :

All reagents and chemicals were obtained from commercial sources (S.D. Fine Chemicals, India; Aldrich, USA). Solvents were purified by standard procedures²⁰. Tris-(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane-HCl (Tris-HCl) buffer solution was prepared by deionized and sonicated triple distilled water. Supercoiled (SC) pUC19 DNA (cesium chloride purified) was procured from Bangalore Genie (India). Calf thymus (ct) DNA, agarose (molecular biology grade), distamycin-A, catalase, superoxide dismutase (SOD), 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-4-piperidone (TEMP), 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein diacetate (DCFDA), Hoechst 33258, ethidium bromide (EB), propidium iodide (PI), 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT), Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM), Dulbecco's phosphate buffered saline (DPBS) and fetal bovine serum (FBS) were purchased from Sigma (USA). Dipyrido[3,2-*a*:2',3'-*c*]phenazine (dppz) was prepared following a literature procedure using 1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione as a precursor^{14,15}. Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was prepared using tetrabutylammonium bromide and perchloric acid.

Physical measurements :

The elemental analysis was done using a Thermo Finnigan FLASH EA 1112 CHNS analyzer. The infrared and electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 35 and Perkin-Elmer spectrum one 55, respectively, at 27 °C. Molar conductivity measurements were done using a Control Dynamics (India) conductivity meter. Electrochemical measurements were carried out at 25 °C on an EG&G PAR model 253 VersaStat potentiostat/galvanostat using electrochemical analysis software 270 using a three electrode setup consisting of a glassy carbon working, platinum wire auxiliary and a saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) in DMF with TBAP (0.1 M) as a supporting electrolyte. The electrochemical data were not corrected for junction potentials. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectral measurements were made using Agilent Technologies 6538 UHD Accurate-mass Q-TOF LC/MS and Bruker Daltonics make Esquire 300 Plus ESI model mass spectrometers. The NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Avance 400 NMR spectrometer (400 MHz). Magnetic susceptibility measurements at 298 K were carried out with solid sample using

MPMS SQUID VSM (Quantum Design, USA). Flow cytometric analysis was performed using FACS Calibur (Becton Dickinson (BD) cell analyzer) at FL1 channel (595 nm).

Synthesis of vitamin-B6 Schiff base (H₂L) :

The Schiff base was synthesized by the condensation of pyridoxal and anthranilic acid using 1.0 mmol (0.20 g) of pyridoxal hydrochloride dissolved in 10 ml dry methanol containing 1.0 mmol (0.06 g) KOH. The mixture was stirred for 30 min. Anthranilic acid (1.0 mmol, 0.14 g) was added to the filtered solution followed by 0.5 g dry MgSO₄ as a desiccant. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, filtered to remove MgSO₄ and the filtrate was dried and subjected to column chromatography in neutral alumina column with a mixture of dichloromethane and methanol (70 : 30 v/v) as a solvent. A yellow color product was separated with a yield of ~85%. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm) : 11.57 (1H, br, carboxylic), 8.28 (1H, s, aromatic pyridoxal), 7.68 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 1.5 Hz, *J*₂ 8.1 Hz, aromatic anthranilic acid), 7.24 (1H, t, *J* 1.5 Hz, aromatic anthranilic acid), 6.73 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 0.9 Hz, *J*₂ 8.2 Hz, aromatic anthranilic acid), 6.50 (1H, t, *J* 1.0 Hz, aromatic anthranilic acid), 3.40 (2H, s, 5' CH₂ group of pyridoxal), 3.17 (1H, s, 5' OH group of pyridoxal), 2.51 (3H, s, CH₃ group of pyridoxal) [br, broad; s, singlet; t, triplet; dd, doublet of doublet]; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, ppm) : 171.54, 165.24, 158.63, 154.24, 140.45, 136.83, 135.21, 133.41, 121.20, 119.22, 115.46, 111.78, 106.45, 108.45, 72.45, 20.02; ESI-MS in CH₃OH : *m/z* 287.4556 (M+H)⁺.

Synthesis of the complexes 1-3 :

The complexes were synthesized by following a common procedure in which the methanol solutions of CuCl₂·2H₂O (0.17 g, 1.0 mmol) and the pyridyl base (1.0 mmol, 0.15 g of 2,2'-bipyridine or 0.19 g of 1,10-phenanthroline or 0.28 g of dppz) were reacted in methanol (10 ml) and stirred for 30 min at room temperature. A methanol solution of the vitamin-B6 Schiff base (1.0 mmol, 0.28 g) previously neutralized with Et₃N was added to the reaction mixture. The complexes were precipitated out as green solid after refluxing the solution for 2 h. The resulting precipitate was then collected by filtration, washed with cold methanol, diethyl ether and finally dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Complex 1 : Yield : 70%, ESI-MS in MeOH : *m/z* 503.91 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₀CuN₄O₄ : C, 59.58; H, 4.00; N, 11.12. Found : C, 59.64; H, 4.08; N, 11.22. Conductivity in DMF (Λ_M) : 24 S cm² M⁻¹. μ_{eff} at 298 K : 1.82 μ_B. UV-Visible in DMF [λ_{max}/nm (ε/M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 689 (115), 480 (5×10³), 304 (37×10³); IR : 3169br, 1603vs, 1504vs, 1432s, 1381w, 1266w, 1220w, 1156w, 1084w, 1020s, 978w, 925w, 812w, 764s, 730m, 662m, 587w cm⁻¹ (vs, very strong; s, strong; m, medium; w, weak; br, broad).

Complex 2 : Yield : 77%, ESI-MS in MeOH : *m/z* 527.89 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₀CuN₄O₄ : C, 61.42; H, 3.82; N, 10.61. Found : C, 61.89; H, 3.99; N, 10.78. Conductivity in DMF (Λ_M) : 21 S cm² M⁻¹. μ_{eff} at 298 K : 1.80 μ_B. UV-Visible in DMF [λ_{max}/nm (ε/M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 714 (125), 440 (7×10³), 278 (25×10³); IR : 3317br, 1668w, 1604vs, 1510s, 1425s, 1365s, 1336m, 1154w, 1101w, 1039w, 1005w, 843m, 762w, 715m, 655w, 528w, 425w cm⁻¹.

Complex 3 : Yield : 73%, ESI-MS in MeOH : *m/z* 630.07 (M+H)⁺. Anal. Calcd. for C₃₃H₂₂CuN₆O₄ : C, 62.90; H, 3.52; N, 13.34. Found : C, 62.66; H, 3.36; N, 13.23. Conductivity in DMF (Λ_M) : 15 S cm² M⁻¹. μ_{eff} at 298 K : 1.78 μ_B. UV-Visible in DMF [λ_{max}/nm (ε/M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 698 (132), 445 (6×10³), 365 (22×10³), 343 (24×10³), 280 (41×10³); IR : 3238br, 1664w, 1606vs, 1495vs, 1419vs, 1370vs, 1289w, 1233m, 1140w, 1072m, 1033m, 880w, 820m, 760s, 726s, 670w, 573w, 506w, 426w cm⁻¹.

Theoretical studies :

The Gaussian 09 software was used for the theoretical calculations²¹. Full geometry optimizations were performed for the complexes using Perdew-Wang 1991 exchange functional as modified by Adamo and Barone and Perdew and Wang's 1991 gradient-corrected correlation functional²². The LanL2DZ59-61 basis set was used for calculation²³. The figures were prepared by Chemcraft software.

DNA binding experiments :

The DNA binding experiments were carried out using calf thymus (ct) DNA in Tris-HCl buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH = 7.2) at room temperature following the procedures reported earlier from our group^{7,14,15,24}. The intrinsic equilibrium binding constants (*K*_b) of the com-

plexes to ct-DNA were obtained by the McGhee-von Hippel (MvH) method using the expression of Bard and co-workers^{25,26}. For ethidium bromide (EB) displacement assay, prior to titration with complexes, DNA was allowed to be saturated with EB by mixing equal volume of solutions of EB (0.32 μM) and ct-DNA (10 μM) and storing it for ~ 24 h. Portions of 10 ml of this solution were taken and different volumes of 20 mM solutions of **1** and **2** and 0.5 mM of **3** were added. The solutions were allowed to stand for 2 h to reach equilibrium. Fluorescence of the solutions was then measured using an excitation wavelength of 545 nm resulting in emission at 589 nm at room temperature. The apparent binding constant K_{app} was calculated from the equation: $K_{\text{app}}[\text{test}] = K_{\text{app-EB}}[\text{EB}]$, where $K_{\text{app-EB}}$ is the apparent binding constant of EB as 10^7 M^{-1} , [EB] is the concentration of EB used, and [test] is the concentration of the test compound causing 50% decrease of the original fluorescence. The viscosity titrations were carried out using a Schott Gerate AVS 310 automated viscometer attached to a constant temperature bath at $37(\pm 0.1)$ °C following a procedure reported earlier by our research group^{7,14,15,24}. The concentration of ct-DNA stock solution was 150 μM (NP) in 5 mM Tris-HCl buffer. The complex was added gradually so that the concentration of the complexes varied from 0 to 120 μM .

The supercoiled (SC) pUC19 DNA (0.2 μg , 50 μM , 2686 base-pairs) photo-cleavage activity of the complexes **1-3** (10 μM) was investigated by agarose gel electrophoresis in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer of pH 7.2 and 50 mM NaCl containing 10% DMF following a similar procedure as reported by us^{7,14,15,24}. The photo-excitation was carried out in near-IR red light using a diode laser of 705 nm (Model : LQC705-38E from Newport Corporation with LD module, continuous-wave (CW) elliptical beam) for 1 h. The laser power was 38 mW, measured using a Spectra Physics CW laser power meter (Model : 407A). Mechanistic investigations were done using various quenchers and scavengers of the reactive oxygen species (ROS) to ascertain the formation and nature of ROS.

Cytotoxicity measurements :

The photo-cytotoxicity of the complexes **1-3** was studied in HeLa (cervical cancer) cells using MTT assay following the protocol as reported earlier by us^{7,14,15,24}. The assay was based on the ability of mitochondrial dehydrogenases present in the viable cells to cleave the tet-

razolium rings of MTT forming dark purple membrane impermeable crystals of formazan that could be readily measured at 540 nm after dissolving that in DMSO²⁷. Photo-irradiation was done with a broad band visible light of 400–700 nm (Luzchem Photoreactor, Model LZC-1, Ontario, Canada, Sylvania fluorescent white tubes with a fluence rate of 2.4 mW cm^{-2} to provide a total dose of 10 J cm^{-2}). The photo-cytotoxicity was measured from the absorbance ratio of the complex treated cells and untreated controls. The IC_{50} values were determined by non-linear regression analysis using GraphPad Prism software²⁸.

DCFDA assay :

The generation of any reactive oxygen species (ROS) was probed using 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (DCFDA) assay²⁹. Cell permeable DCFDA gets oxidized by cellular ROS generating fluorescent DCF with an emission maxima at 525 nm^{30,31}. To detect ROS generation, HeLa cells were incubated with 2 μM of the dppz complex **3** for 4 h followed by photo-irradiation (400–700 nm) for 1 h in 50 mM PBS. The cells were harvested by trypsinization and single cell suspension of 1×10^6 cells ml^{-1} was prepared. The cells were then treated with 10 μM DCFDA solution in DMSO in the dark for 15 min at room temperature. The distribution of DCFDA stained HeLa cells was determined by FACS analysis.

Annexin-V FITC and propidium iodide assay :

To study the pathway of cell death, HeLa cells (4×10^5 cells ml^{-1}) were treated with complex **3** (2 μM) in 10% DMEM for 4 h, followed by exposure to visible light (400–700 nm) for 1 h. The cells were then cultured for 18 h in complete medium, harvested and washed twice with chilled PBS at 4 °C. The cells were re-suspended in 100 μL Annexin-V binding buffer (100 mM HEPES/NaOH, pH 7.4 containing 140 mM NaCl and 2.5 mM CaCl_2), stained with Annexin-V FITC and propidium iodide (PI), and incubated for 20 min in the dark at room temperature. After incubation, 400 μL of binding buffer was added to the cells and analyzed immediately using flow cytometry³².

Results and discussion

Synthesis and general aspects :

Copper(II) complexes having vitamin-B6 Schiff base (H_2L), viz. [Cu(bpy)(L)] (**1**), [Cu(phen)(L)] (**2**) and

[Cu(dppz)(L)] (**3**), where bpy is 2,2'-bipyridine (in **1**), phen is 1,10-phenanthroline (in **2**) and dppz is dipyrido[3,2-*a*:2',3'-*c*]phenazine (in **3**), were prepared by a general synthetic procedure in which respective pyridyl base (bpy/phen/dppz) was reacted with CuCl₂·2H₂O followed by addition of the Schiff base in methanol. The complexes were characterized from spectral and analytical data (Table 1). The complexes showed good solubility in DMF, DMSO, dichloromethane and chloroform. They were moderately soluble in methanol, ethanol and acetonitrile. The complexes were found to be stable in both solid and solution phases. All the complexes showed

Table 1. Selected physicochemical and ct-DNA binding data of the complexes **1-3**

Complex	1	2	3
IR ^a (cm ⁻¹) [ν(C=N)]	1603	1604	1606
Electronic ^b : λ (nm)	689 (115)	714 (125)	698 (132)
(ε/M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)			
μ _{eff} ^c (μ _B)	1.82	1.80	1.78
Λ _M ^d (S cm ² M ⁻¹)	24	21	15
E _i ^e (V) (ΔE _p /mV)	-0.83 (105)	-0.93 (88)	-0.83 (106)
K _b ^f (M ⁻¹)	2.2 (±0.5)	4.1 (±0.7)	3.6 (±0.7)
	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁶
K _{app} ^g (M ⁻¹)	4.3 × 10 ⁴	2.7 × 10 ⁵	1.1 × 10 ⁶

^aIn solid phase. ^bVisible electronic spectral band in DMF. ^cMagnetic moment for solid sample at 298 K. ^dΛ_M, molar conductance in DMF at 25 °C. ^eCathodic peak potential in DMF having 0.1 M TBAP as the supporting electrolyte at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. ^fEquilibrium DNA binding constant determined from the UV-Visible absorption titration. ^gApparent DNA binding constants determined from the ethidium bromide (EB) displacement assay.

a single prominent peak corresponding to the molecular ion peak as [M+H]⁺ in their ESI-MS spectra in methanol. The IR spectra of the complexes are in accordance to their proposed structures. The complexes were non-electrolytic with molar conductance values of ~20 S cm² M⁻¹ in DMF at 25 °C. The magnetic moment values of ~1.8 μ_B at 25 °C indicate the presence of paramagnetic 3d⁹-Cu^{II} with one unpaired electron. The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes recorded in DMF showed a broad and weak band near 700 nm assignable to the copper-centered d-d transition (Fig. 2). The complexes displayed a broad band near 450 nm assignable to the phenolate → copper(II) ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) transition³³. The dppz complex **3** displayed an additional band at 365 nm assignable to the *n* → π* transitions of the phenazine moiety³⁴. The other ligand based transitions were observed in the UV region. The band near 280 nm

Fig. 2. The absorption spectra of the complexes **1** (●●●), **2** (---) and **3** (—) in DMF. The inset shows the d-d bands of the complexes in the near-IR region.

was assigned to the ligand-based π→π* transition. The redox active complexes showed cyclic voltammetric responses involving the metal centre and the ligand in DMF vs SCE with 0.1 M TBAP as the supporting electrolyte. The quasi-reversible reductive response within -0.83 to -0.93 V is assigned to the Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple. The results indicate redox stability of copper(II) and this is likely to reduce the chemical nuclease activity and dark cellular toxicity of the complexes³⁵. Complex **3** showed two additional quasi-reversible redox responses at -1.17 and -1.80 V corresponding to the dppz based reduction^{7,14,15}.

Theoretical study :

DFT (density functional theory) calculations were carried out to understand the photophysical properties of the complexes (Fig. 3). The energy optimized structure shows Cu^{II}N₃O₂ coordination in all the three complexes. The metal ion is penta-coordinated with the *N,N*-donor pyridyl base coordinated through two nitrogen atoms and the Schiff base bonded through the imine nitrogen, phenolic and one carboxylate oxygen atom. The optimized structure of complex **3** is shown in Fig. 3(a). The τ value of 0.53 indicates the coordination geometry being intermediate between trigonal bipyramidal and square-pyramidal. The molecular orbital picture of complex **3** shows that the HOMO is primarily concentrated over the Schiff base moiety, whereas the LUMO resides over the dppz ligand (Fig. 3(b)).

DNA binding study :

UV-Visible absorption spectral titration was carried out to monitor the interaction of the complexes with ct-DNA (Fig. 4). The intrinsic equilibrium DNA binding constant (K_b) values are given in Table 1. The complexes exhibit considerable hypochromicity with a small bathochromic shift of ~2 nm. The K_b values of the com-

Fig. 3. (a) Energy minimized structure of complex **3**. (b) The FMOs of complex **3**.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectral traces of the dppz complex **3** in 5 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.2) on gradual addition of ct-DNA. The inset shows the MvH fitting for the complexes **1** (■), **2** (●) and **3** (▲).

plexes are in the order : **3** > **2** > **1** (Table 1). Complex **3** with an extended planar aromatic dppz moiety has higher DNA binding strength than the other complexes. This observation compares well with the reported results from our group showing high DNA binding strengths for the complexes having ligands with extended planarity¹¹⁻¹⁵.

The ethidium bromide (EB) displacement assay was

used for the determination of apparent DNA binding constants (K_{app}) of the complexes to ct-DNA³⁶. EB is non-emissive in a buffer solution due to solvent quenching. However, in the presence of DNA, EB emits strong fluorescence. This is due to intercalation of EB between the neighboring DNA base pairs³⁶. The competitive binding of the complex to the DNA-EB complex reduces this emission by displacing EB. Therefore, EB fluorescence can be used to examine the competitive binding of the complexes with DNA³⁶. The results gave an order : **3** > **2** > **1** (Table 1). The change in the fluorescence intensity due to binding of complex **3** to ct-DNA is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Change in fluorescence intensity of the ethidium bromide (EB) bound ct-DNA when titrated with a solution of complex **3**. The inset shows % inhibition of the emission intensity of the EB-DNA against concentration of the dppz complex **3**.

A similar DNA binding order is also obtained from the viscosity study. EB as a DNA intercalator and Hoechst dye as a groove binder were used as references. The plots of $(\eta/\eta_0)^{1/3}$ vs $[\text{complex}]/[\text{DNA}]$ showed an intercalative binding mode of complex **3** whereas complexes **1** and **2** showed primarily groove binding propensity (Fig. 6). The difference in binding nature of the complexes can be correlated with the planarity of the phenanthroline based ligands¹¹⁻¹⁵. The bpy ligand being non-planar showed lower DNA binding strengths, while the dppz complex is a DNA intercalator with its planar phenazine moiety.

DNA cleavage activity :

The chemical nuclease activity of the complexes was studied using supercoiled pUC19 DNA (0.2 μg , 30 μM) in Tris-HCl/NaCl buffer (50 mM, pH 7.2) by agarose gel

Fig. 6. Effect of increasing the concentration of the complexes **1** (\blacktriangledown), **2** (\blacktriangle) and **3** (\bullet) along with the DNA intercalator EB (\blacksquare) and DNA groove binder Hoechst 33258 (\blacklozenge) on the relative viscosity of ct-DNA at $37.0 (\pm 0.1)^\circ\text{C}$ in 5 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH = 7.2).

electrophoresis. 3-Mercaptopropionic acid (MPA, 500 μM) was used as a reducing agent. The experiment was performed in the dark to exclude any DNA photocleavage reaction of the complexes. The complexes showed low chemical nuclease activity in comparison to the reported copper(II) complexes^{11–13}. A 10 μM solution of complex **3** showed only 20% nicking of DNA. This is due to redox stability of the complexes. Chemical nuclease activity being undesirable for a compound to be used as a PDT agent, we are successful in designing the dppz-Cu^{II} complex of vitamin-B6 Schiff base that is expected to show low dark cellular toxicity.

DNA photo-cleavage activity of the complexes was studied using SC pUC19 DNA (30 μM , 0.2 μg) in a medium of Tris-HCl/NaCl (50 mM, pH 7.2) buffer. The samples were photo-irradiated with monochromatic near-IR light of 705 nm (38 mW). The results were analyzed by agarose gel electrophoresis (Fig. 7). The choice of this wavelength is based on the presence of a copper(II) centre with a d-d band near 700 nm. Complexes **1** and **2** did not show any DNA photocleavage activity in absence of a photoactive moiety. Complex **3** with the photoactive dppz ligand induced efficient photocleavage of DNA. A 10 μM solution of this complex showed $\sim 70\%$ cleavage of plasmid DNA from its supercoiled (SC) to nicked circular (NC) form in red light of 705 nm on 1.0 h photo-irradiation.

The mechanistic aspect of the DNA photocleavage activity was studied in presence of various additives (Fig. 8). No photocleavage of DNA was observed in an

Fig. 7. Gel electrophoresis diagram showing the photo-induced SC pUC19 DNA (0.2 μg , 30 μM) cleavage activity of the complexes **1-3** (10 μM) in 50 mM Tris-HCl/NaCl buffer (pH = 7.2) containing 10% DMF on photo-irradiation with near-IR red light of 705 nm (1 h exposure) : lane 1, DNA control (light); lane 2, DNA + dppz (light); lane 3, DNA + **3** (dark); lane 4, DNA + **1** (light); lane 5, DNA + **2** (light); lane 6, DNA + **3** (light) [“light” means the sample was exposed to red light of 705 nm; “dark” means the sample was kept in the dark].

argon atmosphere thus indicating the involvement of reactive oxygen species (ROS). The addition of singlet oxygen quenchers, viz. NaN_3 and TEMP did not inhibit the photocleavage activity. This ruled out singlet oxygen as the ROS. Hydroxyl radical scavengers (catalase, DMSO

Fig. 8. Bar diagram showing the photo-cleavage of pUC19 DNA (0.2 μg , 30 μM) by complex **3** (10 μM) in the presence of different additives in near-IR red light of 705 nm for an exposure time of 1 h (D_2O , 16 μL ; NaN_3 , 0.5 mM; TEMP, 0.5 mM; DMSO, 4 μL ; KI, 0.5 mM; catalase, 4 units; SOD, 4 units). The concentrations of distamycin and methyl green were 50 μM and 25 μM respectively. The + sign indicates treatment of the specified additive with complex **3** and SC DNA.

and KI) showed significant inhibition in the DNA cleavage activity. Formation of superoxide radical as the intermediate was evidenced from the inhibitory role of SOD. The mechanistic data indicate the formation of both hydroxyl and superoxide radicals as the ROS in a photo-

redox pathway which was earlier reported for the copper(II)-dipyridoquinoxaline (dpq) complexes³⁷⁻³⁹. To study the DNA major or minor groove binding preference of complex **3**, cleavage experiments were performed in presence of the DNA minor-groove binder distamycin and major-groove binder methyl green. DNA photocleavage by **3** was significantly reduced in the presence of methyl green, whereas no such inhibition was observed in presence of distamycin (50 μM) indicating DNA major groove binding preference of the complex **3**.

Photocytotoxicity :

The ability of the complexes **1-3** to inhibit the cellular growth and induce cell death upon photo-activation with visible light of 400-700 nm in human cervical cancer HeLa cells was studied by MTT assay (Fig. 9(a)). The complexes showed reduction in the viability of the HeLa cells in a dose-dependent manner. Complexes **2** and **3** showed enhanced cytotoxicity by 2 and 20 fold, respectively, on light exposure when compared to the non-irradiated samples (Table 2). The dppz complex **3** displayed remarkable photodynamic effect with an IC_{50} value of only 0.9 μM in light and 22.6 μM in the dark. While copper(II) complexes are in general known to show significant dark toxicity, complex **3** interestingly showed low dark toxicity possibly due to its redox inactivity as evidenced from the electrochemical studies. The observed PDT effect for complex **3** is novel and comparable to that of Photofrin^{®40}. The IC_{50} value of complex **3** on light exposure increased to 6.1 μM upon pre-incubation with 4 mM vitamin-B₆ (Fig. 9(b)). This indicates that a vitamin-B₆ transporting membrane carrier (VTC) mediated diffusion pathway is operative for the cellular uptake of the

Fig. 9. (a) Photocytotoxicity of complex **3** in HeLa cells on 4 h incubation in the dark followed by exposure to visible light of 400–700 nm (10 J cm^{-2}) for 1 h. (b) Photocytotoxicity of **3** in HeLa cells in the presence of VB6 with the cells first incubated with 4 mM VB6 for 45 min followed by addition of complex **3** for the MTT assay. The decrease in the PDT effect indicates the VB6 Schiff base in **3** contributing towards its cellular uptake. Light and Dark conditions are indicated by (●) and (■) symbol, respectively.

Table 2. IC_{50} values (in μM) of the complexes **1-3** and related compounds in HeLa cells

Compd.	Dark ^a	Visible light ^b	Reference
1	13.4 (± 1.1)	9.9 (± 0.9)	Present work
2	15.7 (± 1.4)	7.2 (± 0.6)	Present work
3	22.7 (± 1.6)	0.9 (± 0.2)	Present work
[Cu(Ph-Tyr)(dppz) (ClO ₄)] ^c	4.3 (± 0.3)	2.1 (± 0.2)	11
[Cu(Fc-Trp)(dppz)] (ClO ₄) ^d	8.9 (± 0.2)	1.3 (± 0.1)	12
Photofrin ^{®e}	>41	4.3 (± 0.2)	40
Cisplatin	71.3 (± 2.9)	68.7 (± 3.4)	14

^aFor 4 h incubation in the dark. ^bThe IC_{50} values correspond to 4 h incubation in the dark followed by photo-exposure to visible light (400–700 nm, 10 J cm^{-2}). ^cPh-Tyr is the reduced Schiff base of benzaldehyde and L-tyrosine. ^dFc-Trp is the ferrocene-appended reduced Schiff base of L-tryptophan. ^eThe IC_{50} values (633 nm excitation; fluence rate : 5 J cm^{-2}).

complex. The low dark toxicity and high phototoxicity of complex **3** makes it suitable for potential applications in PDT. The results are of importance in the chemistry of metal-based anticancer drugs since cisplatin in absence of any photoactive moiety gave an IC_{50} value of $\sim 70 \mu\text{M}$ in both dark and light under similar experimental conditions on 4 h incubation¹⁴.

ROS generation from DCFDA assay :

2',7'-Dichlorofluorescein diacetate (DCFDA) assay was carried out to detect formation of any intracellular ROS. DCFDA is a cell permeable fluorogenic probe which on oxidation by intracellular ROS generates DCF with an emission maximum at 525 nm. This can be detected by FACS analysis²⁹⁻³¹. The cells treated with the dppz complex **3** under darkness did not show any significant generation of DCF. However, cells treated with the complex on exposure to visible light (400–700 nm) showed a significant shift in the emission band towards the right, indicating an increase in the intensity of intracellular emission resulting from the generation of DCF via the ROS induced oxidation of DCFDA (Fig.10). The assay data indicate ROS formation only on exposure to visible light.

Detection of apoptosis from Annexin V-FITC/PI assay :

Annexin V-FITC/PI assay is a convenient way to de-

Fig. 10. DCFDA assay showing generation of ROS by complex **3** in HeLa cells upon exposure to visible light (400–700 nm). Generation of ROS is highlighted by the shift in the fluorescence band intensity.

tect apoptosis and was therefore performed in HeLa cells with complex **3** to explore the mode of photo-induced cell death. The early stages of apoptosis are marked by the flipping of phosphatidylserine from the inner surface of the plasma membrane to the outer surface and can be readily detected by a fluorophore conjugated annexin V protein, known to bind phosphatidylserine that are exposed on the outer surface of the plasma membrane. This assay is based on the dual staining of the cells by annexin V-FITC (fluorescein isothiocyanate) and propidium iodide (PI, a DNA binding dye with red fluorescence). The cells undergoing early apoptosis are identified as a single positive population for FITC. The necrotic cell populations are stained only by PI. The population of double positive cells comprises cells in late apoptosis having a compromised plasma membrane. To study whether complex **3** is capable of inducing any visible light-mediated apoptotic cell death, we stained the HeLa cells that were pretreated with 2 μM of the complex in the dark and in light with Annexin-V FITC and PI. We observed that complex **3** induced apoptosis on visible light irradiation (Fig. 11). About 20% of the cells were viewed to be in an early apoptotic stage and $\sim 52\%$ of the cells were in a late apoptotic stage. The population of cells in necrosis mode was found to be significantly low ($\sim 8\%$). The results suggest an overall apoptotic mode of cell death. The complex at this concentration did not induce any significant cell death under darkness.

Conclusions

The ternary copper(II) complex of dipyrrophenazine

Fig. 11. FACS profiles of Annexin-V FITC and PI (propidium iodide) staining of the HeLa cancer cells undergoing apoptosis induced by complex **3** in the dark and in visible light (400–700 nm).

(dppz) and vitamin-B6 Schiff base was found to show remarkable photo-induced anticancer activity. The complex displayed remarkable PDT effect in visible light (400–700 nm) with low dark toxicity in HeLa cancer cells. The complex caused apoptotic cell death by generating reactive oxygen species only upon photo-irradiation. Complex **3** as an efficient binder to ct-DNA showed intercalative DNA binding and efficient photo-induced cleavage of plasmid DNA in near-IR light of 705 nm forming hydroxyl radicals as the ROS. Unlike most redox active copper(II) complexes, complex **3** showed poor chemical nuclease activity in the presence of reducing agent due to its redox stability. This is an important observation considering that the complexes showing significant chemical nuclease activity are not suitable for PDT use. The photocytotoxicity of complex **3** is comparable to that of the FDA approved PDT drug Photofrin[®]. The results showing the positive effect of the incorporation of vitamin-B6 in the Schiff base structure in facilitating cellular uptake of the complex via VTC mediated diffusion pathway could open up new avenues in the chemistry of metal-based anticancer agents in PDT.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Government of India, for financial support (SR/S5/MBD-02/2007). ARC thanks the DST for J. C. Bose national fellowship and the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation, Germany, for donation of an electrochemical system. TM thanks UGC for Dr. D. S. Kothari Postdoctoral Fellowship. AD thanks the University Grants Commission (UGC), New Delhi, for research fellowship. SB thanks Indian Institute of Science (IISc) for a postdoctoral fellowship. The FACS facility supported by Department of Biotechnology, Government of India, is acknowledged.

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